

Security in IoT: Block Chain or OneM2M?

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

Assessment of Potentials of Block Chain and OneM2M for incorporating security in IoT. Discuss the results of combining Block Chain with Machine Learning, OneM2M, Data Analytics and Internet of Things (IoT) etc. Discussion on IOTA protocol. Some core components of IOTA network etc.

2. Aim

To identify the pros and cons and challenges of combining Block Chain with IoT, OneM2M, BIG Data and Machine Learning etc.

3. Material and methods

The communication stack of IoT will be elaborated. The way to incorporate security in this communication stack will be discussed. The existing tools and corresponding platforms (hardware and software) will be identified. The key elements of Block Chain and bitcoins will be identified and the features which provide support for these elements will be elaborated. Then we will compare OneM2M and Block Chain and whether their combination will be helpful or not. Finally I will put some light on IOTA protocol.

4. Results

Some results of running the Block Chain functions on IoT nodes will be provided.

5. Conclusions

A more secure and adaptive security framework can be proposed for cryptocurrencies.

6. Keywords

Bitcoin, Block Chain, IoT, OneM2M, BIG Data.

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Author biography

Muhammad Umair Muhammad Umair has completed his MSc. at the age of 24 years from University of Engineering & Technology, Lahore, Pakistan. He is working as Research Officer in IoT Lab at University of Engineering & Technology, Lahore. His research interests include Internet Security, Block Chain, IoT and BIG data. He has recently published a research paper identifying required hardware and software features for building a powerful SIoT application.

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